

1 **A retrotransposon-like gene, RTL5, is modulated during differentiation of embryonic stem cells to**
2 **the trophectoderm lineage.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of a
9 retrotransposon-like gene, *RTL5*, with putative functions in lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of
10 the human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Irie, M., Itoh, J., Matuszawa, A., Ikawa, M., Suzuki, T., Hiraoka, Y., Ishino, F. and Kaneko-Ishino,
13 T., 2021. Retrovirus-derived acquired genes, RTL5 and RTL6, are novel constituents of the innate immune
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